

Performance analysis of conventional multilevel inverter driven PMSM drive in EV applications

Rakesh G. Shriwastava^{1,7}, Pravin B. Pokle², Ajay M. Mendhe³, Nitin Dhote⁴, Rajendra M. Rewatkar⁵, Rahul Mapari⁶, Ranjit Dhunde⁷, Hemant R. Bhagat Patil⁸, Ramesh Pawase⁹

¹Department of Electrical Engineering, Govindrao Wanjari College of Engineering and Technology, Nagpur, India

²Department of Electronics Engineering, Priyadarshini J.L. College of Engineering, Nagpur, India

³Departments of Electrical Engineering, Priyadarshini J.L. College of Engineering, Nagpur, India

⁴Department of Electrical Engineering, St. Vincent Pallotti College of Engineering and Technology, Nagpur, India

⁵Department of Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Datta Meghe Institute of Higher Education and Research, Wardha, India

⁶Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, Pimpri Chinchwad College of Engineering and Research, Pune, India

⁷Department: School of Technology, Management, and Engineering, SVKM'S NMIMS Navi, Mumbai, India

⁸Department of Mechanical Engineering, Govindrao Wanjari College of Engineering and Technology, Nagpur, India

⁹Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, Amrutvahini College of Engineering Sangamner, Ahmednagar, India

Article Info

Article history:

Received Dec 23, 2023

Revised Sep 13, 2024

Accepted Oct 23, 2024

Keywords:

EPROM

EPS

MOSFET

Permanent magnet synchronous

motor

VSI

ABSTRACT

This paper describes the simulation and hardware analysis of a two-level inverter-driven permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) drive in EV applications. The design of various sections of PMSM Drive is discussed in detail. This proposed work is based on the voltage source converter (VSC) fed four-pole, 373 W. This paper highlights the design and implementation using a microcontroller of (PMSM) drive for various operating conditions. The experimental results show that the control and power circuit used in the design can achieve excellent and consistent speed performance. The performance along with test results of the speed and load variation of the PMSM drive is studied for steady-state conditions. The performance of the motor has been checked by increasing the inverter frequency with the speed of the motor and also keeping the frequency remains constant by varying the load and speed. Hardware analysis indicates the improved performance of the motor and the drive. It has good speed and torque responses and is suitable for EPS applications.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Rakesh Shriwastava

Department of Electrical Engineering, Govindrao Wanjari College of Engineering and Technology

Nagpur, India

Email: rakesh_shriwastava@rediffmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

The low value of cogging torque, ruggedness, high efficiency, high power-to-weight ratio, and additional reluctance torque are the permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) characteristics. Hence it is used in electric vehicle applications due to the motor running to different load and speed profiles. It is not needed to supply magnetizing currents through the stator flux due to the magnet in the rotor and the constant air gap in PMSM. This paper focuses on low speeds and the back emf respectively. When at high speed, it gives high current and less switching losses. It would operate at low and high switching frequencies for low and high speeds respectively [1]-[7].

This paper explains the performance analysis of VSI-driven SVM-PMSM drives for EV applications. Voltage source inverter-driven PMSM drive is one of the widely used methods for speed and torque control [8]-[14]. Three three-phase rectifier circuits give the fixed DC voltage. The shunt capacitor is used for filter

purposes. The output transfer to MOSFET bridge inverters [15]-[20]. For getting pulses, the control circuit is used and an isolator and driver circuit is used for isolation [21]-[25].

The theme of the paper is the design of conventional inverter-driven PMSM drives in EPS applications. Sections 1 and 2 describe the introduction and mathematical model of PMSM, section 3 describes the simulation model and analysis, and section 4 describes design considerations. Sections 5 and 6 present experimental results and conclusion respectively.

2. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF PMSM

2.1. Rotor reference frame PMSM

The modelling of the PMSM machine has been presented henceforth in the rotor reference frame. In a PMSM, the rotor is a permanent magnet without any windings and hence there are no equations associated with the rotor. The 3- ϕ stationary 'abc' frame can be transformed into 2- ϕ synchronously rotating 'dq' frame, with the help of abc \rightarrow dq transformations. In the 'dq' frame, the stator has two windings: d-axis winding and q-axis winding; and the d-axis winding is aligned with the magnetic pole axis. Consider the PMSM machine running at the speed of ' ω_r ', in the anti-clockwise direction. The D-axis induced voltage is (1).

$$u_d = R_d i_d + \frac{d\lambda_d}{dt} - \omega_r \lambda_q \quad (1)$$

The Q-axis induced voltage is shown in (2)-(5).

$$u_q = R_q i_q + \frac{d\lambda_q}{dt} - \omega_r \lambda_d \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda_d = L_d i_d + \lambda_m \quad (3)$$

$$\lambda_d = L_{qi} i_q \quad (4)$$

$$L_d = L_q \quad (5)$$

The torque equation is (6).

$$T_e = \frac{3p}{2} (\lambda_d i_q - \lambda_q i_d) \quad (6)$$

Put in (7).

$$T_e = \frac{3p}{2} [(\lambda_d i_d + \lambda_m) i_q - L_{qi} i_d i_q] \quad (7)$$

$$T_e = \frac{3p}{2} [(L_d - L_q) i_d i_q + \lambda_m i_q] \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Reluctance torque} = \frac{3p}{2} (L_d - L_q) i_d i_q \quad (9)$$

$$\text{field torque} = \frac{3p}{2} \lambda_m i_q \quad (10)$$

$$T_e = \frac{3p}{2} \lambda_m i_q \quad (11)$$

Hence the electromagnetic torque present in a round rotor permanent magnet synchronous machine is nothing but the field torque which is present due to the permanent magnet flux linkage, λ_m . For a chosen permanent magnet synchronous machine, the number of poles (p) is constant as well as the permanent magnet rotor flux-linkage (λ_m). Hence, the electromagnetic torque equation for the round-rotor PMSM can be rewritten as (12) and (13).

$$T_e = K_t i_q \quad (12)$$

$$K_t = \frac{3p}{2} \lambda_m \quad (13)$$

Therefore, electromagnetic torque is (14).

$$T_e = T_l + B \omega_m + J \frac{d\omega_m}{dt} \tag{14}$$

3. SIMULATION MODEL ANALYSIS

Figure 1 shows the Simulink model of a two-level inverter-driven PMSM drive. Figures 2-4 show motor response at 280 rpm, 500 rpm, and 1500 rpm. Figure 5 shows a fast Fourier transform (FFT) analysis of a two-level inverter-driven PMSM drive. Table 1 shows the torque ripple analysis of a two-level inverter. In Figure 2, at 0.01 sec, load torque 3 N-m is applied and removed at 0.03 sec. The torque varies with the load. The reference speed is 500 rpm and the fluctuation in speed on removal of torque than speed remains constant. Speed, three-phase stator current, and electromagnetic torque are constant with some ripples at 0.6 sec.

Figure 1. Simulink model of two-level inverter-driven PMSM drive

Figure 2. Motor response at 280 rpm (a) rotor speed, (b) electromagnetic torque, and (c) three-phase stator current

Figure 3. Motor response at 500 rpm (a) rotor speed, (b) torque, and (c) three-phase stator current

In Figure 3, at 0.01 sec, load torque 3 N-m is applied and removed at 0.15 sec. The torque varies with the load. The reference speed is 500 rpm and the fluctuation in speed on removal of torque than speed remains constant. Speed, three-phase stator current, and electromagnetic torque are constant with some ripples at 0.15. The torque varies with the load. The reference speed is 500 rpm and the fluctuation in speed on removal of torque than speed remains constant. Speed, three-phase stator current, and electromagnetic torque are constant with some ripples at 0.06 sec.

Figure 4. Motor response at 1500 rpm (a) rotor speed, (b) torque, and (c) three-phase stator current

In Figure 4, at 0.01 sec, load torque 5 N-m is applied and removed at 0.03 sec. The torque varies with the load the reference speed is 500 rpm and fluctuation in speed on removal of torque than speed remains constant. Speed, three-phase stator current, and electromagnetic torque are constant with some ripples at 0.06 sec.

Table 1. Torque ripples analysis (two level inverter)

Controller speed	% Torque ripples
280 rpm	21.98%
500 rpm	18.57%
1500 rpm	12.48%

Figure 5. FFT analysis of two-level inverter-driven PMSM drive

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS ANALYSIS

Figure 6 shows the block diagram of the PMSM drive. Figure 7 shows the output voltage and capacitor voltage waveform. Figure 8 shows the gate pulse pattern for the MOSFET. Table 2 shows motor speed variation by frequency. Tables 3-5 show motor speed variation by load at 30, 40 Hz, and 50 Hz. Figure 7 shows speed-frequency characteristics. Figure 8, Figure 9, and Figure 10 shows load-speed characteristics at 30 Hz, 40 Hz, and 50 Hz.

Figure 6. Block diagram of the PMSM drive

Table 2. Motor parameter frequency variation

Sr. No.	Time	Frequency	Actual speed	Measured Speed	Voltage
1	0.033 m.s	30 Hz	900 rpm	950 rpm	240 V
2	0.025 m.s	40 Hz	1200 rpm	1210 rpm	240 V
3	0.02 m.s	50 Hz	1500 rpm	1490 rpm	240 V
4	0.05 m.s	60 Hz	1800 rpm	1790 rpm	240 V

Table 3. Motor parameter load variation (30 Hz)

Sr. No.	Weight	Frequency	Motor Speed	Motor Speed	Motor Torque	Motor Power
1	500 gm	30 Hz	900 rpm	950 rpm	0.12 N-m	14.20 W
2	1000 gm	30 Hz	900 rpm	950 rpm	0.22 N-m	34.78 W
3	1500 gm	30 Hz	900 rpm	950 rpm	0.35 N-m	42.48 W
4	2000 gm	30 Hz	900 rpm	950 rpm	0.56 N-m	62.47 W
5	2500 gm	30 Hz	900 rpm	950 rpm	0.78 N-m	72.02 W
6	3000 gm	30 Hz	900 rpm	950 rpm	0.85 N-m	95.47 W

Table 4. Motor parameter load variation (40 Hz)

Sr. No.	Weight	Frequency	Motor Speed	Motor Speed	Motor Torque	Motor Power
1	500 gm	40 Hz	1200 rpm	1210 rpm	0.14 N-m	28.98 W
2	1000 gm	40 Hz	1200 rpm	1210 rpm	0.21 N-m	47.69 W
3	1500 gm	40 Hz	1200 rpm	1210 rpm	0.35 N-m	71.54 W
4	2000 gm	40 Hz	1200 rpm	1210 rpm	0.58 N-m	92.97 W
5	2500 gm	40 Hz	1200 rpm	1210 rpm	0.74 N-m	120.15 W
6	3000 gm	40 Hz	1200 rpm	1210 rpm	0.85 N-m	144.94 W

Table 5. Motor parameter load variation (50 Hz)

Sr. No.	Weight	Frequency	Motor Speed	Motor Speed	Motor Torque	Motor Power
1	500 gm	50 Hz	1510 rpm	1490 rpm	0.21 N-m	32.46 W
2	1000 gm	50 Hz	1510 rpm	1490 rpm	0.43 N-m	54.61 W
3	1500 gm	50 Hz	1510 rpm	1490 rpm	0.52 N-m	82.37 W
4	2000 gm	50 Hz	1510 rpm	1490 rpm	0.65 N-m	105.34 W
5	2500 gm	50 Hz	1510 rpm	1490 rpm	0.80 N-m	132.25 W
6	3000 gm	50 Hz	1510 rpm	1490 rpm	0.95 N-m	162.94 W

Figure 7. Motor speed characteristics at a frequency

Figure 8. Motor characteristics at 33.3 Hz

Figure 9. Motor characteristics at 50 Hz

Figure 10. Motor characteristics at 59 Hz

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presentation a detailed Simulink model for performance analysis of conventional multilevel inverter driven PMSM drive in EV applications has being developed. It is shown in the experimental and simulation results of performance analysis of conventional multilevel inverter driven PMSM drive that the speed of the permanent magnet synchronous motor can be varied by varying the frequency of an inverter. Hence an attempt has been made to verify the performance of the motor. It is found that, speed remains constant at constant frequency, with varying load conditions and the test result shows the improved performance of the motor. In this paper simulation of permanent magnet synchronous motor gives constant torque in experimental and simulation results with less torque ripples and constant speed as shown in the above waveform and result tables. Hence this PMSM drive used in EPS application.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. G. Shrivastava, M. P. Thakare, K. V. Bhadane, M. S. Harne, and N. B. Wagh, "Performance enhancement of DCMLI fed DTC-PMSM drive in electric vehicle," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1867–1881, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i4.3714.
- [2] M. P. Thakre and N. Kumar, "Evaluation and control perceptive of vsm-based multilevel PV-STATCOM for distributed energy system," *MAPAN*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 561–578, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s12647-021-00481-x.
- [3] M. P. Thakre and A. Ahmad, "Interline power flow controller (ipfc) deployment in long transmission lines and its effects on distance relay," *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (India): Series B*, vol. 103, no. 2, pp. 491–505, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s40031-021-00637-y.
- [4] R. G. Shrivastava, N. C. Ghuge, D. D. Palande, and A. Tidke, "Performance evaluation of conventional inverters driven PMSM drive using microcontroller," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 2327, no. 1, p. 012001, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/2327/1/012001.
- [5] L. Y. L. Yaohua, L. Jingyu, M. J. M. Jian, and Y. Q. Y. Qiang, "A simplified voltage vector selection strategy for direct torque control," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 9, no. 3, p. 539, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.12928/telkomnika.v9i3.746.
- [6] L. M. Masisi, S. Williamson, and P. Pillay, "A comparison between a 2-level and 3-level inverter for a permanent magnet synchronous motor drive under different inverter switching frequencies," in *2012 IEEE International Conference on Power Electronics, Drives and Energy Systems (PEDES)*, IEEE, Dec. 2012, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/PEDES.2012.6484370.
- [7] X. Wang, Y. Xing, Z. He, and Y. Liu, "Research and simulation of DTC based on SVPWM of PMSM," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 29, pp. 1685–1689, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.proeng.2012.01.195.
- [8] P. Ramana, B. S. Kumar, K. A. Mary, and M. S. Kalavathi, "Comparison of various PWM techniques for field oriented control VSI fed PMSM drive," *International Journal of Advance Research in Electrical, Electronics, and Instrumentation Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 7, pp. 2928–2936, 2013.
- [9] H. R. Pinkymol, A. I. Maswood, and A. Venkataraman, "Space vector based field oriented control of permanent magnet synchronous motor with a 3-level inverter scheme," in *2013 IEEE Transportation Electrification Conference and Expo: Components, Systems, and Power Electronics - From Technology to Business and Public Policy, ITEC 2013*, 2013, doi: 10.1109/ITEC.2013.6573485.
- [10] M. B. Daigavane, S. R. Vaishnav, and R. G. Shrivastava, "Sensorless field oriented control of pmsm drive system for automotive application," in *International Conference on Emerging Trends in Engineering and Technology, ICETET*, 2016, pp. 106–112, doi: 10.1109/ICETET.2015.11.
- [11] R. G. Shrivastava, M. B. Daigavane, and P. M. Daigavane, "Simulation analysis of three level diode clamped multilevel inverter fed PMSM drive using carrier based space vector pulse width modulation (CB-SVPWM)," in *Procedia Computer Science*, 2016, pp. 616–623, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2016.03.078.
- [12] R. G. Shrivastava, D. R. Bhise, and P. Nagrale, "Comparative analysis of foc based three level dcmlI driven PMSM drive," in *Proceeding - 1st International Conference on Innovative Trends and Advances in Engineering and Technology, ICITAET 2019*, 2019, pp. 26–31, doi: 10.1109/ICITAET47105.2019.9170242.
- [13] V. S. Guntuk, U. V. Bakle, V. S. Lahare, A. R. Bochare, and M. P. Thakre, "A novel 4-level converter for switched reluctance motor drive in plug-in hevs," in *2019 International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICCS)*, IEEE, May 2019, pp. 626–631, doi: 10.1109/ICCS45141.2019.9065527.
- [14] M. P. Thakre and P. S. Borse, "Analytical evaluation of foc and DTC induction motor drives in three levels and five levels diode clamped inverter," in *2020 International Conference on Power, Energy, Control, and Transmission Systems (ICPECTS)*, IEEE, Dec. 2020, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ICPECTS49113.2020.9337015.
- [15] M. Thakre, J. Mane, and V. Hadke, "Performance analysis of srm based on asymmetrical bridge converter for plug-in hybrid electric vehicle," in *2020 International Conference on Power, Energy, Control, and Transmission Systems (ICPECTS)*, IEEE, Dec. 2020, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ICPECTS49113.2020.9337059.
- [16] M. P. Thakre and N. P. Matala, "Alleviation of voltage sag-swell by dvr based on SVPWM technique," in *2020 International Conference on Power, Energy, Control, and Transmission Systems (ICPECTS)*, IEEE, Dec. 2020, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ICPECTS49113.2020.9336972.
- [17] K. Bhadane *et al.*, "A comprising study on modernization of electric vehicle subsystems, challenges, opportunities and strategies for its further development," in *2021 4th Biennial International Conference on Nascent Technologies in Engineering (ICNTE)*, IEEE, Jan. 2021, pp. 1–9, doi: 10.1109/ICNTE51185.2021.9487757.
- [18] K. V. Bhadane, M. S. Ballal, A. Nayyar, D. P. Patil, T. H. Jaware, and H. P. Shukla, "A comprehensive study of harmonic pollution in large penetrated grid-connected wind farm," *MAPAN*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 729–749, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s12647-020-00407-z.
- [19] M. Thakre, A. Ahmad, and K. Bhadane, "Measurement class phasor measurement unit compliance for electrical grid monitoring," *MAPAN*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 125–135, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s12647-021-00440-6.
- [20] H. Prasad, K. V. Bhadane, and P. Kumar, "Real-time performance evaluation of single phase 7 level Z-source boost inverter," in *2021 7th International Conference on Electrical Energy Systems (ICEES)*, IEEE, Feb. 2021, pp. 28–31, doi: 10.1109/ICEES51510.2021.9383751.
- [21] J. Sears, D. Roberts, and K. Glitman, "A comparison of electric vehicle level 1 and level 2 charging efficiency," in *2014 IEEE Conference on Technologies for Sustainability (SusTech)*, IEEE, Jul. 2014, pp. 255–258, doi: 10.1109/SusTech.2014.7046253.

- [22] M. Yilmaz and P. T. Krein, "Review of charging power levels and infrastructure for plug-in electric and hybrid vehicles," in *2012 IEEE International Electric Vehicle Conference*, IEEE, Mar. 2012, pp. 1–8, doi: 10.1109/IEVC.2012.6183208.
- [23] R. Raff, V. Golub, D. Pelin, and D. Topic, "Overview of charging modes and connectors for the electric vehicles," in *2019 7th International Youth Conference on Energy (IYCE)*, IEEE, Jul. 2019, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/IYCE45807.2019.8991586.
- [24] S. Lukic and Z. Pantic, "Cutting the cord: static and dynamic inductive wireless charging of electric vehicles," *IEEE Electrification Magazine*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 57–64, Sep. 2013, doi: 10.1109/MELE.2013.2273228.
- [25] G. R. C. Mouli, J. Schijffelen, M. van den Heuvel, M. Kardolus, and P. Bauer, "A 10 kw solar-powered bidirectional ev charger compatible with chademo and combo," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 1082–1098, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2018.2829211.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Dr. Rakesh G. Shriwastava obtained Ph.D. degree in electrical engineering specializing in power electronics and drives from RTM Nagpur University, (India) in 2017. He occupied various positions to serve the engineering institutes for about 24 years. He is currently working as a professor in the Department of Electrical Engineering, Govindrao Wanjari College of Engineering & Technology, Nagpur. His research interests include the analysis and control of electrical drives, particularly in hybrid, and electric vehicle applications. He can be contacted at email: rakesh_shriwastava@rediffmail.com.

Dr. Pravin B. Pokle born in 1976, received a B.E. degree in Electronics Engineering in 1998, M.Tech. degree in VLSI from RTM Nagpur University, Nagpur in 2008, and a Ph.D. in Electronics Engineering from RTM Nagpur University, Nagpur in 2015. Currently, he is working as an assistant professor and head of the Department of Electronics and Telecommunications Engineering at Priyadarshani J. L. College of Engineering, Nagpur, India. He can be contacted at email: pbpokle@gmail.com.

Dr. Ajay M. Mendhe graduated in Electrical Engineering from YCCE, Nagpur. He has a post-graduation in Electrical Power Systems from SSGMCE, Shegaon, Amravati University, and a Diploma in Business Management from Nagpur University. He is completed his Ph.D. from SSSUTMS, Sehore (MP). He is working as an associate professor and Head of the Electrical Engineering Department of Priyadarshini J. L. College of Engineering Nagpur. He can be contacted at email: mendheajay1@gmail.com.

Dr. Nitin Dhote did graduation in Electrical Engineering from VNIT, Nagpur. He graduated in Electrical Power Systems from the Government College of Engineering, Amravati and Diploma in Business Management and a Ph.D. from RTM, Nagpur University. He is working as a professor and head of the Electrical Engineering Department of SVP CET, Nagpur. He can be contacted at email: ndhote@stvincenngp.edu.in.

Dr. Rajendra M. Rewatkar obtained his B.E. degree in Electronics Engineering from RTM Nagpur University Nagpur, India in 1996. He received the M.Tech. Degree in Electronics Engineering from G.H. Rasoni College of Engineering, Nagpur, India in 2010. He was awarded a Doctoral Degree in Electronics Engineering from RTM Nagpur University, Nagpur (India) in 2016. He is currently working as an associate professor and head of the Biomedical Engineering Department of the Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Datta Meghe Institute of Higher Education and Research Sawangi (Meghe), Wardha. He can be contacted at email: rajendrar.feat@dmihher.edu.in.

Dr. Rahul Mapari received a bachelor's degree and master's degree in Electronics Engineering from Savitribai Phule Pune University, India, in 2004 and 2007 respectively, and a Ph.D. degree in Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering from Amravati University, India in 2016. He has been working as a Professor in the Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering of Pimpri Chinchwad College of Engineering and Research, Pune since 2017. He can be contacted at email: rahul.mapari@pccoer.in.

Dr. Ranjit Dhunde graduated in Mathematics from the Institute of Science Nagpur and a Ph.D. from RTM, Nagpur University. He is working as an assistant professor in Mathematics at SVKM's NMIMS School of Technology, Management and Engineering, Navi Mumbai. He has a total teaching experience of 17 years at UG and PG levels. He has published 12 research papers in reputed International Journals. He can be contacted at email: ranjithdunde@gmail.com.

Dr. Hemant R. Bhagat Patil obtained master's degree in Mechanical Engineering from RTMNU, Nagpur (India). He occupied various positions to serve the engineering institutes for about 22 years. He is currently working as an associate professor in the Department of Mechanical, Govindrao Wanjari College of Engineering and Technology, Nagpur. He attended International and National conferences. He is a member of professional bodies such as ISTE. He can be contacted at email: hemant_bp@yahoo.com.

Dr. Ramesh Pawase completed his Bachelor of Engineering (B.E.) in Electronics and Communications Engineering from Amrutvahini College of Engineering, Sangamner in 2004 and Master of Engineering in Electronic and Telecommunication from Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Technological University, Lonere in 2008. He has completed his Ph.D. in the area of Analog CMOS circuits for MEMS in 2019 from Savitribai Phule Pune University (SITRC Nashik). He is working as associate professor in Department of E&TC Engineering from 2005 in Amrutvahini College of Engineering, Sangamner Maharashtra (India). He can be contacted at email: ramesh.pawase@avcoe.org.